

A mechanistic and non-mechanistic approach on the solid state thermal decomposition of transition metal complexes of 3-(3-furan-2-yl-acryloyl)-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-pyran-2-one

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Abstract : The thermal decomposition of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates of 3-(3-furan-2-yl-acryloyl)-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-pyran-2-one was studied by TG-DTA and X-ray powder diffraction methods. The thermal stability of the complexes was studied using thermogravimetry and the decomposition schemes of the complexes were given. The mechanism of the decomposition has been established from TG data. The kinetic parameters i.e. *n* (order of reaction), *E* (energy of activation), *Z* (pre-exponential factor), ΔS (entropy change) and ΔG (free energy change) were calculated from the TG curve using mechanistic (Sestak-Berggren and Satava) and non-mechanistic (Coats-Redfern, MacCallum-Tanner and Horowitz-Metzger) integral equations.

Keywords : Dehydroacetic acid, chalcones, thermal study, TG-DTA, kinetic parameters, powder X-ray diffraction.

Introduction

In recent years a number of β -dicarbonyl compounds in which the carbonyl function(s) bonded to olefinic linkage(s) have gained considerable importance mainly because of such unsaturated β -dicarbonyl compounds and their metal complexes possess interesting biochemical properties such as antitumour, antioxidant, antifungal and antimicrobial activities¹⁻³. Literature survey reveals much less work has been carried out on the thermal studies of complexes of unsaturated carbonyl compounds⁴. Wendlandt⁵⁻⁷ and Hill⁸ studied the thermal properties of metal chelates with different types of complexing ligands. The Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates of 3-(3-furan-2-yl-acryloyl)-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-pyran-2-one were prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, electronic absorption, IR, PNMR, magnetic susceptibility, conductivity and X-ray powder diffraction methods. The complexes are biologically active and exhibit enhanced antifungal activities⁹. To the continuation of our research^{9,10} and taking into consideration the importance of complexes of unsaturated carbonyl compounds, here we report the kinetics and mechanism of thermal decom-

position of transition metal complexes of 3-(3-furan-2-yl-acryloyl)-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-pyran-2-one in which the keto function is directly bonded to olefinic group.

Experimental

The metal contents was determined by AAS on Perkin-Elmer PE-Analyst 300. The differential thermal analysis (DTA) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were carried out using Perkin-Elmer TA/SDT-2960 in the temperature range of 25–1000 °C for Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II} complexes and 25–1200 °C for Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} complexes. The rate of heating was 10 °C/min. Dry nitrogen was flowed over the sample at the rate 20 cm³ min⁻¹ and a chamber cooling water flow rate was 10 L⁻¹ h⁻¹. The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the decomposition product was recorded on Philips 3701 diffractometer.

Synthesis of ligand :

A solution of 0.01 mole of dehydroacetic acid (3-acetyl-6-methyl-pyran-2,4-dione), 10 drops of piperidine and 0.01 mole of furfuraldehyde in 25 ml chloroform was refluxed for 8–10 h. 10 ml of the chloroform-water azeotrope mixture was separated by distillation. Crystals

of product were separated on slow evaporation of the remaining chloroform and recrystallised from ethyl acetate⁹.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

To a chloroform solution (30 ml) of the ligand (2 mmol), methanolic solution (20 ml) of metal chlorides was added with constant stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained around 7.5 by adding 10% methanolic solution of ammonia. It was then refluxed for 2 h. The resulting metal complex was filtered in hot condition and washed with ethyl acetate, methanol, pet-ether and dried over calcium chloride in vacuum desiccator.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are colored, non-hygroscopic and stable at room temperature. They are insoluble in water

and common organic solvents but are soluble in DMF, DMSO and dioxane. All the complexes gave satisfactory results of elemental analysis⁹. The elemental analysis show 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry for all the complexes (Figs. 1 and 2). It corresponds well with the general formula $[M(L)_2(H_2O)_2]$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}$; $[M(L)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot H_2O$, where $M = Ni^{II}$ and $[M(L)_2(Cl)(H_2O)]$, where $M = Fe^{III}$ and $L = C_{13}H_9O_5$.

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of Ni^{II} complex.

X = H₂O; when M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II}

X = Cl; when M = Fe^{III}

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes.

Thermal studies :

The kinetic parameters i.e. n (order of reaction), E (energy of activation), Z (pre-exponential factor), ΔS (entropy) and ΔG (free energy change) were calculated from non-isothermal TG curves using different non-mechanistic equations, such as Coats-Redfern method¹¹, MacCallum-Tanner method¹² and Horowitz-Metzger method¹³.

Coats-Redfern method :

$$\log \left[\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}}{(1 - n)T^2} \right] = \log \frac{ZR}{Eq} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes

Compd.	F.W.	m.p. (°C)	Geometry	Found (Calcd.) M
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Mn]	581.4	252	Octahedral	9.21 (9.45)
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₁ ClFe]	599.8	260	Octahedral	9.10 (9.31)
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Co]	585.4	245	Octahedral	9.81 (10.06)
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Ni]·H ₂ O	603.2	276	Octahedral	9.89 (10.03)
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Cu]	589.9	243	Distorted octahedral	9.93 (10.77)

MacCallum-Tanner method :

$$= \log \frac{ZE}{Rq} - 0.485E^{0.435} - \frac{0.449 + 0.217E}{T} \times 10^3 \quad (2)$$

Horowitz-Metzger method :

$$= \log \frac{ZRT_s^2}{Eq} - \frac{E}{2.303RT_s} + \frac{E\theta}{2.303RT_s^2} \quad (3)$$

The left-hand side of eqs. (1) and (2) was plotted against $1/T$ and against $\theta = (T - T_s)$ for eq. (3). By using different value of order of reaction, straight line was fitted by regression. The highest value of correlation coefficient gave the correct value of 'n'. From the slope and intercept, E and Z values were calculated. Using E and Z values, the values of ΔS and ΔG were determined.

Several authors¹⁴⁻¹⁶ have discussed evaluation of the mechanism of reaction using mechanistic equations. We have used the evaluation of mechanism of the reactions discussed by Sestak-Berggren¹⁷ and Satava¹⁸. The mechanisms of thermal decomposition of each of the complexes were deduced using the non-isothermal method derived from the Arrhenius-type equation by Satava. The $g(\alpha)$ form corresponding to nine mechanistic equations have been proposed and the mechanism is obtained from the one which gives the best representation of the experimental data¹⁵. The Coats-Redfern method were used for solving the exponential integral. The linear plots of nine forms were constructed by the method of least squares and the corresponding correlation coefficient values were evaluated. The values of E and Z were also evaluated in each case from the slope and the intercept, respectively.

Slight differences in the kinetic parameter values for the same step using different methods are observed like obtained by many workers¹⁹⁻²¹. The variation may be due to different methods based on different inherent limitation in the methods of calculations. The kinetic parameters calculated from mechanistic and non-mechanistic methods are in good mutual agreement (Table 2).

Table 2. Kinetic data of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, evaluated by the methods : (a) Coats-Redfern, (b) MacCallum-Tanner, (c) Horowitz-Metzger and (d) mechanistic equations

Complex	Step	ΔT (°C)	Mass loss (%) Expt. (Calcd.)	Probable species	log method		Z (s ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
					$\log \left[\frac{1 - (1 - \alpha)^n}{1 - n} \right]$	$\frac{E}{(1 - n)}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)				
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Mn]	1	150-200	6.0 (6.2)	Two coordinated H ₂ O	a	1.18	59.15	1.1 × 10 ³	-151.5	67.14
					b	1.12	58.42	2.0 × 10 ⁶	-127.4	65.11
					c	1.08	62.08	2.3 × 10 ⁵	-145.5	69.74
					d	-	58.90	1.7 × 10 ⁴	-167.1	67.71
	2	220-330	26.5 (27.5)	Non coordinated part of ligand	a	0.89	47.84	1.8 × 10 ³	-187.5	60.31
					b	0.89	48.63	4.1 × 10 ⁴	-161.7	59.39
					c	0.91	58.56	1.8 × 10 ⁴	-168.4	69.75
					d	-	48.49	3.4 × 10 ²	-201.7	61.91
	3	400-760	56.5 (56.75)	Coordinated part of ligand	a	0.99	13.81	9.348	-234.7	36.76
					b	0.87	17.18	9.530	-234.6	40.12
					c	0.73	22.78	1.018	-253.2	47.54
					d	-	15.70	0.110	-271.6	42.26
4	760-		MnO							
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₁ ClFe]	1	150-260	11.5 (11.9)	One H ₂ O and one Cl ₂	a	0.77	12.34	0.14	-265.3	27.86
					b	0.97	10.77	0.77	-251.2	25.46
					c	1.02	25.79	6.10	-234.0	39.48
					d	-	12.38	0.0093	-287.9	29.22
	2	270-500	27.0 (26.67)	Non coordinated part of ligand	a	0.91	122.8	7.9 × 10 ¹⁰	-41.14	125.5
					b	0.90	123.7	5.8 × 10 ¹²	-5.34	124.1
					c	0.91	136.5	1.8 × 10 ¹²	-15.11	137.5
					d	-	123.3	1.5 × 10 ¹⁰	-54.70	126.8

Table-2 (contd.)

				a	0.72	11.26	1.5	-248.1	30.29
	3	650-1080	49.5 (49.5)	Coordinated part of ligand	b	0.69	13.31	3.6	-240.5
				c	0.65	21.04	0.97	-251.6	40.35
				d	-	27.84	1.2	-250.1	47.03
	4	1080-		FeO					
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Co]				a	1.10	72.27	3.0 × 10 ⁶	-124.3	79.05
	1	150-200	6.5 (6.14)	Two coordinated H ₂ O	b	1.12	71.86	7.4 × 10 ⁷	-97.72
				c	0.96	77.02	1.0 × 10 ⁷	-114.2	83.24
				d	-	72.11	4.9 × 10 ⁵	-139.5	79.71
				a	0.72	34.84	6.1 × 10 ¹	-216.5	50.28
	2	230-360	28.5 (27.33)	Non coordinated part of ligand	b	0.78	36.43	1.3 × 10 ³	-190.9
				c	0.69	46.46	6.0 × 10 ²	-197.5	60.54
				d	-	36.47	12.57	-229.6	52.85
				a	0.87	16.02	9.9	-235.5	42.73
	3	450-830	53.5 (56.37)	Coordinated part of ligand	b	0.78	21.12	14.0	-232.8
				c	0.61	27.24	1.2	-252.8	55.92
				d	-	16.63	0.1	-273.7	47.67
	4	850-		CoO					
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Ni]. H ₂ O				a	0.59	10.31	0.1972	-258.7	19.9
	1	30-55	3.0 (2.98)	One physically adsorbed H ₂ O	b	0.65	7.334	1.078	-244.6
				c	0.62	13.44	0.4397	-252.1	22.8
				d	-	10.39	0.0195	-277.9	20.7
				a	0.9	58.70	6.8 × 10 ⁵	-136.3	65.76
	2	110-175	6.0 (6.15)	Two coordinated H ₂ O	b	0.9	57.53	1.1 × 10 ⁷	-113.3
				c	1.1	68.84	1.2 × 10 ⁷	-112.5	74.66
				d	-	58.99	1.2 × 10 ⁵	-150.5	66.78
				a	1.18	30.19	11.20	-230.5	46.51
	3	250-420	27.0 (27.34)	Non coordinated part of ligand	b	1.14	31.95	229.0	-205.4
				c	1.24	36.51	33.07	-221.5	52.19
				d	-	58.76	6.5 × 10 ²	-196.8	72.69
				a	1.12	18.34	1.692	-249.5	44.54
	4	430-1100	51.5 (52.17)	Coordinated part of ligand	b	0.89	20.56	12.41	-232.9
				c	0.95	23.35	0.854	-255.2	50.15
				d	-	31.89	0.294	-264.1	59.61
	5	1100-		NiO					
[C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₁₂ Cu]				a	0.91	90.77	8.9 × 10 ⁸	-76.95	94.92
	1	150-175	6.0 (6.10)	Two coordinated H ₂ O	b	0.89	90.17	2.8 × 10 ¹⁰	-48.45
				c	1.03	99.92	1.1 × 10 ¹⁰	-56.44	103.0
				d	-	139.0	2.0 × 10 ¹¹	-31.95	140.8
				a	1.17	27.51	16.26	-226.9	42.60
	2	200-350	26.5 (27.1)	Non coordinated part of ligand	b	1.10	27.89	230.0	-204.8
				c	0.97	36.31	92.57	-212.5	50.44
				d	-	26.82	1.673	-245.8	43.17
				a	0.72	17.02	0.482	-259.1	41.57
	3	370-900	55.5 (55.9)	Coordinated part of ligand	b	0.78	19.05	9.758	-234.1
				c	0.56	17.84	0.316	-262.6	42.73
				d	-	16.59	0.102	-272.6	44.39
	4	900-		CuO					

The TG curve of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III} shows three steps decomposition, where as TG curve of Ni^{II} complex shows four stepped decomposition.

In the TG curve of Mn^{II} complex, the first step shows an inclined slope between 150–200 °C with a mass loss of 6.0% (calcd. 6.2%), indicates the removal of two molecules of coordinated water, an endothermic peak in the range 150–200 °C ($\Delta T_{\min} = 165$ °C) in DTA corresponds to dehydration step. The kinetic parameters of this step is calculated using nine mechanistic equations¹⁸ and the rate controlling process of dehydration is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The anhydrous compound in second step decomposes within a short temperature range from 220–330 °C with a 26.5% mass loss (calcd. 27.5%). An exotherm between 240 and 350 °C with $\Delta T_{\max} = 280$ °C in DTA is also observed. This step may be attributed to the removal of non-coordinated part of the ligand i.e. furfural ring along with beta carbon (C₁₀H₈O₂). This is confirmed by isolating the compound after second decomposition step and characterized by elemental analysis. This step follows mampel equation and hence the rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The third step corresponds to decomposition of coordinated part of the ligand and in the range of 400–750 °C with a mass loss 56.5% (calcd. 56.75%). A broad endotherm is observed for this

step. The rate controlling process of this step is found to be one dimensional diffusion (D_1). The mass of the final residue corresponds to stable MnO, 11.0% (calcd. 12.21%). The energy of activation from mechanistic and non-mechanistic methods shows a decreasing order of E as the decomposition follows.

In thermal study of Fe^{III} complex, an inclined slope from 130–260 °C in TG curve with mass loss 11.5% (calcd. 11.9%) indicates the removal of one molecule of water and one chloride ion (may be oxidized as Cl₂). An endothermic peak in the range 180–240 °C is observed in DTA ($\Delta T_{\min} = 213$ °C). The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The complex readily undergoes second step decomposition in between temperature 270 and 500 °C with 27% mass loss (calcd. 26.67%). An exothermic peak between 250–270 °C ($\Delta T_{\max} = 260$ °C) in DTA, attributed to the removal of non-coordinating part of the ligand (C₁₀H₈O₂). The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The third step corresponds to slow decomposition of remaining part of the ligand in the temperature range of 675–1080 °C with a mass loss 49.5% (calcd. 49.5%). A broad endotherm is observed for this step. The mechanistic study suggested that this decomposition had taken place with higher E value, whereas lower values are calculated adopt-

Fig. 3. TGA-DTA of Mn^{II} complex.

ing non-mechanistic equations. The rate controlling process of this decomposition is found to be one dimensional diffusion (D_1). The mass of the final residue 12.0% (calcd. 11.97%) corresponds to FeO. The calculated E values (Table 2) suggest that the energy of activation energy is smaller for first step decomposition than second step decomposition, which may be due to weak bonding between Fe^{III} and coordinated water molecule and chlorine. The larger E value of second step compared to that of the first and third step decomposition may be due to strong thermal agitation accompanying the elimination of water molecule and chloride ion²².

The thermal decomposition profile of Co^{II} complex show no weight loss up to 150 °C. The mass loss of 6.5% (calcd. 6.14%) is observed in the range 150–200 °C. An endothermic peak between 140–210 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{min}} = 180$ °C), correspond to loss of two molecules of water. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The second step decomposition is in between temperature 235 and 375 °C with 28.5% mass loss (calcd. 27.33%). A broad exothermic peak between 225–375 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{max}} = 320$ °C) in DTA may be attributed to the removal of non-coordinating part of the ligand ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$). The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The mass loss continues and follows slow decomposition of remaining part of the ligand 53.5% (calcd. 56.37%). The rate controlling process of this decomposition is found to be one dimensional diffusion (D_1). The mass of the final residue corresponds to CoO , 11.5% (calcd. 12.8%). The energy of activation from mechanistic and non-mechanistic methods shows a decreasing order of E as the decomposition follows.

The thermal decomposition profile of Ni^{II} complex shows weight loss 3% (calcd. 2.98%) in the range 30–100 °C indicates the removal of one physically adsorbed water molecule. An endothermic peak between 30–55 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{min}} = 35$ °C), correspond to dehydration. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The mass loss of 6.0% (calcd. 5.95%) is observed in the range 130–180 °C. An endothermic peak between 150–180 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{min}} = 157.5$ °C) correspond to loss of two molecules of water. The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The third step decomposition is in between 250 and 425 °C with 27% mass loss (calcd. 26.52%). A broad exothermic peak between 200–

450 °C ($\Delta T_{\text{max}} = 315.7$ °C) in DTA, attributed to the removal of non-coordinating part of the ligand ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$). The rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The mass loss continues and follows slow decomposition of remaining part of the ligand in the range of 525–1100 °C with 51.5% mass loss (calcd. 52.17%). A broad endotherm is observed for this step. The rate controlling process of this decomposition is found to be three dimensional diffusion (D_3). The mass of the final residue 12.5% (calcd. 12.38%) corresponds to NiO . The calculated E values (Table 2) suggest that the energy of activation is small for first step decomposition and this may be due to very weak bonding between Ni^{II} and physically adsorbed water molecule. The E values are higher for second step decomposition and follows decreasing order.

In the TG curve of Cu^{II} complex, the mass loss starts

Fig. 4. XRD powder diffractogram of the metal oxide residue.

from 50 °C and an inclined slope from 160–185 °C with a mass loss of 6.0% (calcd. 6.10%), indicates the removal of two molecules of coordinated water, an endothermic peak in the range 150–200 °C ($\Delta T_{\min} = 175$ °C) in DTA corresponding to dehydration step is observed. The rate controlling process of dehydration is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The mass loss continues in TG curve upto 325 °C with a mass loss 26.5% (calcd. 27.1%). An exothermic peak $\Delta T_{\max} = 280$ °C in DTA attributed to the removal of non-coordinated part of the ligand i.e. furfural ring along with beta carbon [$C_{10}H_8O_2$] is observed. This step follows mampel equation and hence the rate controlling process of decomposition is found to be random nucleation with one nucleus on each particle (F_1). The third step corresponds to decomposition of coordinated part of the ligand and in the range of 350–900 °C with a mass loss 55.0% (calcd. 55.9%). A broad endo-

therm is observed for this step. The rate controlling process of this step is found to be one dimensional diffusion. The mass of the final residue corresponds to stable CuO, 12.5% (calcd.13.48%). The energy of activation from mechanistic and non-mechanistic methods shows a decreasing order of E as the decomposition follows.

The negative values of ΔS , in all the thermal decomposition steps showed that the transition states are more ordered i.e. in a random molecular configuration than the reacting complexes²³.

XRD analysis :

The oxide residue for Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes obtained at 1000 °C and Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes obtained at 1200 °C were grounded and subjected to XRD analysis. The XRD powder diffractogram of metal oxide residue of all complexes are shown in Fig. 4. It is clear from the Table 3 that the final decomposition product of

Table 3. X-Ray powder diffraction data of MnO, FeO, CoO, NiO and CuO

Metallic residue	System	Lattice constants	Observed		Reference		JCPDS-ICDD number
			Angle (2 θ)	d -Value (Å)	Angle (2 θ)	d -Value (Å)	
MnO	Cubic	$a = b = c$ $= 4.442$	34.960	2.5644	34.958	2.5645	78-0424
			40.574	2.2216	40.587	2.2210	
			58.740	1.5706	58.745	1.5704	
			71.234	1.3227	70.220	1.3393	
			73.845	1.2822	73.843	1.2822	
FeO	Cubic	$a = b = c$ $= 4.294$	36.198	2.4796	36.204	2.4791	75-1550
			42.072	2.1460	42.051	2.1470	
			60.982	1.5181	60.980	1.5181	
			73.024	1.2946	73.021	1.2946	
			76.842	1.2326	76.841	1.2395	
CoO	Cubic	$a = b = c$ $= 4.262$	36.487	2.4604	36.486	2.4606	78-0431
			42.405	2.1298	42.381	2.1310	
			61.492	1.5067	61.488	1.5068	
			73.658	1.2850	73.659	1.2850	
			77.532	1.2302	77.525	1.2303	
NiO	Cubic	$a = b = c$ $= 4.176$	37.255	2.4116	37.263	2.4111	75-0269
			43.274	2.0891	43.296	2.0881	
			62.850	1.4771	62.893	1.4765	
			75.419	1.2594	75.433	1.2591	
			79.409	1.2058	79.427	1.2055	
CuO	Cubic	$a = b = c$ $= 4.245$	36.630	2.4512	36.637	2.4508	78-0428
			42.614	2.1198	42.559	2.1225	
			61.766	1.5007	61.761	1.5008	
			74.008	1.2798	74.00	1.2799	
			77.877	1.2256	77.893	1.2254	

all complexes was there corresponding oxides whose XRD data matches the reference data. This confirms that the predicted mechanism for decomposition of complexes are correct.

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